

FEATURES OF THE ROMANTIC GENRE IN THE WORKS OF JANE AUSTIN

¹Ahadova H., ²Tursunaliyeva O.

¹EFL Teacher

²University student

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11409032>

Abstract. *Jane Austen, who was born on December 16, 1775, tried to deliver romanticism to her fans in her works, which were not many, but which caught the attention of many people. Since ancient times, the romantic genre has expressed different meanings according to its origin in French, Spanish and Romance languages, but they all come together under the name of romanticism. It came to England as an important element of poetry, unusual, mysterious, strange and fantastic things (feelings, situations, adventures) are summed up in this word.*

Keywords: *romantic genre, romanticism, novel, work, critical, realism, character, family, marriage, humour, love.*

Introduction

Jane Austen is an author who wrote mainly in the 18th century, and in the process of her work, she sheds more light on the lifestyle of those times, various social and life events between men and women. There are six examples of her works, which are written almost in the romantic genre. It is not difficult to see that each of her writings is dominated by more emotions and inner experiences. What is the reason for this? the question comes to mind. If we study her family life, the writer wants to make every creative product she writes popular, so she tries to revive her experience. It would not be wrong to say that, if not all, she turned the loved ones who taught her lessons into the heroes of her novels. As far as Jane's biography is concerned, not much is known about her and her family, we only know about her brother, sister and aunt. Her family faced various tensions and life difficulties, and sometimes divorces. As we can see in the case of Jane, her popularity also began after her death. She is not even married. He met only one person in his life, he was 19 years old at that time. Thomas Lefroy happens to be the Irish nephew of their family friend. But her trust in him soon fades as Thomas and Jane meet at several parties, during which Thomas flatters Jane's sister and dances together at the ball. It is for this reason that she begins to use criticism and humor as her main weapons in her novels. By the result of her personal life, she started to address criticism and humor as main tool in her novels.

Methods

In order to better understand the above points, it will be right to get acquainted with each of her novels. As mentioned, Austen has six surviving novels, but almost none of them were published during her lifetime. Nevertheless, it gained much attention among writers. Jane's first novel, *Sense and Sensibility*, was written in 1811. The characters of the novel are two sisters, Elinor and Marianne Dashwood. Another goal of the novel is to find balance between sense (the mind) and sensibility (the heart). In the following years, Jane's novels such as "*Pride and Prejudice*" in 1813, "*Mansfield Park*" in 1814 and "*Emma*" in 1815 were written one after the other. Her novels contain not only criticism, but also an important part of the transition to 20th century realism. The reason is that she often describes ordinary people in our daily life, and this shows that it is a direction that has a unique and important aspect in English novels. Her novel "*Emma*" will

appear on the screen in 2020, the most surprising thing is that a movie will be shot with the same name of the novel. As we said, her novels became more popular after her death. Her posthumous novels «Northanger Abbey», «Persuasion» and "The Watsons" were published in the years 1818 and 1892 accordingly. A significant transition in her reputation occurred in 1833. It is reasonable to assume that the main reason for this is the reprinting of Jane's novels in Richard Bentley's "Standard Novels" series. In this direction, novels became popular and the number of their readers increased. We mentioned that there is not much information about her and her family. But 52 years after her death, under the name "Memoirs of Jane Austen", information about her life and creative work was presented to her fans by her nephew, and it was very openly received. Since then, information about her work has inspired many critical articles and films. In order to clarify the mentioned information, we will analyze one of her novels below.

Results

Pride and Prejudice is Austen's most famous novel, mainly because the novel deals with the consequences of rash decisions made by Elizabeth Bennet, the book's dynamic protagonist, who appreciates the difference between superficial beauty and real goodness. In the novel, Elizabeth's parents, Mr. and Mrs. Bennet, also played a central role. Mr Bennet, who owns the Longbourn estate in Hertfordshire, has five daughters, but his estate can only go to a male heir. His wife also has no inheritance, so the family will be very poor after his death. Therefore, they had to marry at least one daughter to a better family to ensure the future needs of the family, and this is the subject of the novel. While the Bennet family is living with such anxiety, a handsome and chubby young man moves into their town. He was a young man named Mr. Fitzwilliam Darcy, a friend of Bingley's and the wealthy owner of the family estate of Pemberley in Derbyshire, rumored to be worth around £10,000. The villagers described him as proud and almost disliked him, but according to the servants of the house he was very kind. Thus, the Bennet family, who found out about the arrival of a new guest, decided to marry one of their daughters to him. Look at the coincidence that Mr. Darcy invited the Bennet family to dinner that day. At night, Mr. Darcy takes a liking to Mr. Bennet's daughter, Elizabeth, and dances with her twice. Mr. Bennet's other daughters were also more intelligent and beautiful than each other. After that, they were together at several parties. Elizabeth's sisters were Jane, Mary, Catherine and Lydia Bennet. Because of this, Mr. Darcy's friend Charles Bingley falls in love with one of them, namely Jane. Meanwhile, George Wickham gets between the main characters Mr. Darcy and Elizabeth, because he also fell in love with Elizabeth. In fact, Mr. Wickham was with Mr. Darcy from childhood and was the son of Darcy's father's steward. After that, Miss Bennet and Mr. Darcy become distant for a while. But with the help of Mr. Edward Gardiner, Mrs. Bennet's brother, and Mrs. Gardiner, they get better, which later leads to their marriage. Mr. Wickham then tries to elope with Elizabeth's youngest sister, Lydia, but Mr. Darcy intervenes and convinces Mr. Wickham to marry Lydia. Elizabeth's middle sister, Miss Mary, was very simple and modest. So, she marries one of her uncle Phillip's lawyers and they move to Maryton. Mrs Bennet's 4th daughter, Catherine "Kitty", was a little bit naughty and she was always jealous of Lady. Later, after getting away from Lydia and improving his behavior, he married a priest who lived near Pemberley. Thus, Mr. and Mrs. Bennet get rid of dreams of getting their daughter married. And the experiences in the plot and the lives of the characters sometimes seem sad. For this reason, we can describe Austen as bringing realism to English writing and becoming famous for her critical novels.

Conclusion

The novel we discussed above has sold more than 20 million copies. Over a period of time, this novel became very famous, it was brought to the public through its dramatic adaptations, reprints, unofficial sequels, films. This novel was even recommended to students preparing for the SAT exam, a privilege given to enter US universities. Because the tests in the SAT exam were in the historical direction of English, and this book was written in the same direction.

REFERENCES

1. Alexander, Christine and Juliet McMaster, eds. *The Child Writer from Austen to Woolf*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2005. ISBN 0-521-81293-3.
2. Auerbach, Emily. *Searching for Jane Austen*. Madison: University of Wisconsin Press, 2004. ISBN 0-299-20184-8
3. Austen, Jane. *Catharine and Other Writings*. Ed. Margaret Anne Doody and Douglas Murray. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1993. ISBN 0-19-282823-1.
4. Austen, Jane. *The History of England*. Ed. David Starkey. Icon Books, HarperCollins Publishers, 2006. ISBN 0-06-135195-4.
5. Austen, Jane. *Pride and Prejudice*. Hertfordshire: Wordsworth Editions Limited, 1993. ISBN 9781853260001
6. „Jane Austen (English novelist) – Britannica Online Encyclopedia“. britannica.com. Qaraldi: 31-may 2010-yil.
7. Austen, Henry Thomas. "Biographical Notice of the Author". *Northanger Abbey and Persuasion*. London: John Murray, 1817.
8. https://kitobsevar.uz/kept/xrpt_g7dyrdf22c4opa4xvtb68aixboljf8pbbesekj7mcl5cepzystvt4i_uhu2s1z031dk6nu23ycx.pdf
9. Litz, 142.
10. MacDonagh, 66-75; Collins, 160-161.
11. Honan, 124-27; Trott, „Critical Responses, 1830-1970“, *Jane Austen in Context*, 92.
12. Southam, „Criticism, 1870-1940“, *The Jane Austen Companion*, 102.
13. Litz, 3-14; Grundy, „Jane Austen and Literary Traditions“, *The Cambridge Companion to Jane Austen*, 192-93; Waldron, „Critical Responses, Early“, *Jane Austen in Context*, s. 83, 89-90; Duffy, „Criticism, 1814-1870“, *The Jane Austen Companion*, 93-94.
14. *The Works of Jane Austen*. Vol VI. 1954. Ed. R.W. Chapman and B.C. Southam. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1988, as supplemented by additional research reflected in Margaret Anne Doody and Douglas Murray, eds. *Catharine and Other Writings*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1993.
15. Wikipedia. W.W.W.com